

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

On a coefficient-inverse problem with semi-nonlocal boundary conditions for the three-dimensional Tricomi equation in an unbounded parallelepiped

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Keywords: three-dimensional Tricomi equation, coefficient-inverse problem with semi-nonlocal conditions, Fourier and “ ε – regularization” methods, a priori estimates and sequences of approximations.

1. Introduction

Linear inverse problems for second-order mixed-mode equations are used to model and identify processes occurring in transient regimes where the equation switches from elliptic to hyperbolic. Historically, such models arose in transonic aerodynamics to study the transition of a gas flow through the speed of sound, where inverse problems are used to reconstruct the coefficients characterizing the properties of the medium from experimental data. Similar formulations are used in acoustics and the theory of wave propagation in inhomogeneous media to diagnose the parameters of waveguides and extended channels. In geophysics, linear inverse problems serve as a tool for reconstructing the characteristics of subsurface structures from seismic data. In models of filtration and transport in porous media, such problems allow for the identification of permeability coefficients and sources. Linear inverse problems play a significant role in control theory and the calibration of mathematical models, as they provide robust algorithms for reconstructing parameters. From a mathematical point of view, they are important for the development of the theory of correctness, stability and methods for analyzing degenerate operators that underlie more complex nonlinear models.

In the study of nonlocal problems, a close relationship was revealed between problems with nonlocal boundary conditions and inverse problems [1]. Inverse problems for classical equations such as parabolic, elliptic, and hyperbolic equations have been studied quite well [2,3].

Linear inverse problems (with the search for solutions to the problem and right-hand sides of the equations) for second-order mixed-type model equations in a plane were studied in the works of A.G. Megrabov, K.B. Sabitov and their students [4-6], and for multidimensional second-order mixed-type equations in bounded domains with local boundary conditions were studied and developed in the work of S.Z. Dzhamalov, S.G. Pyatkov [7], and with non-local boundary conditions were studied and developed in the works of S.Z. Dzhamalov, R.R. Ashurov [8].

Linear inverse problems for second-order mixed-type equations of both the first and second kind in unbounded domains have been studied in the works of S.Z. Dzhamalov and his students [9,10]. As far as we know, coefficient inverse problems (involving

solutions, coefficients, and right-hand sides of the equations) for degenerate and mixed-type equations have been very little studied to date. Coefficient inverse problems with nonlocal boundary conditions in a parallelepiped for the Tricomi equation were first proposed and studied in the works of S.Z. Dzhamalov, A.A. Shokirov [11]. Coefficient inverse problems for mixed-type equations in unbounded domains have remained virtually unexplored. We will attempt to partially fill this gap in this paper.

To study the unique solvability of the coefficient inverse problem for the three-dimensional Tricomi equation in an unbounded parallelepiped, we propose a method based on reducing the coefficient inverse problem to direct problems for families of loaded Tricomi integro-differential equations with semi-nonlocal boundary conditions in a bounded rectangular domain.

Let Ω be a domain in R^n . Recall that a differential equation is called a loaded equation if it contains a trace of some operations from the desired solution on manifolds belonging to the closure of $\bar{\Omega}$ the domain Ω whose dimension is strictly less than n [12].

In the domain

$$\begin{aligned} G &= (-1, 1) \times (0, T) \times (-\infty, +\infty) = Q \times (-\infty, +\infty) = \\ &= \{(x, t, z) \mid -1 < x < 1, 0 < t < T, -\infty < z < +\infty\} \end{aligned}$$

we consider the three-dimensional Tricomi equation:

$$Lu = xu_{tt} - bu_{xx} - u_{zz} + \alpha(x, t)u_t = c(x, t)u + \psi(x, t, z) \quad (1)$$

here $\alpha(x, t)$ is a sufficiently large function, b is a sufficiently large positive number. Let $\psi(x, t, z) = g(x, t, z) + h(x, t) \cdot f(x, t, z)$, where $g(x, t, z), f(x, t, z)$ are given functions, and $h(x, t)$ and $c(x, t)$ are to be determined.

Preliminary information. The Fourier transform of the function $u(x, t, z)$ with respect to the variable z is denoted by

$$\hat{u}(x, t, \lambda) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{1/2}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} u(x, t, z) e^{-i\lambda z} dz,$$

and the inverse Fourier transform is denoted by

$$u(x, t, z) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{1/2}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \hat{u}(x, t, \lambda) e^{i\lambda z} d\lambda.$$

We introduce spaces of continuous functions together with derivatives up to order l via $C^l(Q)$ or simply C^l , with the norm

$$\|u\|_{C^l(Q)} = \sum_{|\alpha|=0}^l \max_{(x,t) \in Q} |D^\alpha u|.$$

Let $W_2^l(Q)$ denote Sobolev spaces with norm

$$\|u\|_{W_2^l(Q)}^2 = \|u\|_l^2 = \sum_{|\alpha|=0}^l \int_Q (D^\alpha u)^2 dx dt.$$

We introduce the anisotropic Sobolev space by $W_2^{l,s}(G)$, consisting of functions whose derivatives up to the l -th order in x and t , and up to the s -th order in z belong to $L_2(G)$, with the norm

$$[u]_{l,s}^2 \equiv \|u\|_{W_2^{l,s}(G)}^2 = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (1 + \lambda^2)^s \|\hat{u}\|_{W_2^l(Q)}^2, \quad s \geq 3, \quad l = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

where \hat{u} is the inverse Fourier transform of u .

2. Problem statement

Find a triple of functions $\{u(x, t, z), h(x, t), c(x, t)\}$ satisfying equation (??) almost everywhere in the domain G , such that $u(x, t, z)$ satisfies the following boundary conditions:

1) semi-nonlocal boundary conditions

$$\gamma D_t^p u|_{t=0} = D_t^p u|_{t=T}, \quad p = 0, 1, \quad (2)$$

$$u_x|_{x=-1} = u_x|_{x=1} = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$\lim_{|z| \rightarrow \infty} u = 0, \quad \lim_{|z| \rightarrow \infty} u_z = 0, \quad (4)$$

where γ is a positive number such that $|\gamma| > 1$;

2) additional conditions

$$u(x, t, \ell_1) = \varphi_1(x, t), \quad (5)$$

$$u(x, t, \ell_2) = \varphi_2(x, t), \quad (6)$$

$$-\infty < \ell_1 < \ell_2 < +\infty.$$

and, together with the functions $h(x, t)$, (x, t) belongs to the class

$$U = \{(u, h, c) \mid u \in W_2^{2,3}(G), h \in W_2^2(Q), c \in W_2^2(Q)\}.$$

Definition 1. A generalized solution of problem (1)-(6) is a function $\{u, h, c\}$ from class U that satisfies equation (1) almost everywhere in domain G subject to conditions (2)-(6).

Let the following conditions be satisfied regarding the coefficients and the right-hand side of equation (1):

Condition 1:

1) non-local conditions:

$$\alpha(x, 0) = \alpha(x, T), \quad \alpha(-1, t) = \alpha(1, t),$$

$$\gamma g(x, 0, z) = g(x, T, z), \quad \gamma f(x, 0, z) = f(x, T, z);$$

2) smoothness:

$$f(x, t, \ell_i) = f_i \in C_{x,t}^{0,1}(\bar{Q}), \quad g(x, t, \ell_i) = g_i \in C_{x,t}^{0,1}(\bar{Q}),$$

$$f \in W_2^{3,3}(G), \quad g \in W_2^{1,3}(G);$$

3) $2\alpha(x, t) + (\mu + 2)x > 1$, $\mu\alpha(x, t) - \alpha_t(x, t) - \mu^2 > 2$, $b > 2$, for all $(x, t) \in Q$, where $\mu = \frac{2}{T} \ln |\gamma| > 0$.

Condition 2:

$$\varphi_i \in W_2^3(Q), \quad \gamma D_t^p \varphi_i|_{t=0} = D_t^p \varphi_i|_{t=T}, \quad p = 0, 1, \quad \varphi_{ix}|_{x=-1} = \varphi_{ix}|_{x=1} = 0, \quad \varphi_i \neq 0.$$

3. Main part

We introduce the following notation, through

$$q \equiv \gamma_1 + 2\gamma_0\gamma_2 = m_1 \left(\varepsilon_{\varphi, g} + m_3 [g]_{1,3}^2 + (m_2 + \varepsilon_{\varphi, g} m_3) [f]_{2,3}^2 \right),$$

where

$$\varepsilon_{\varphi, g} = \left((1 + b + \|\alpha\|_{C^1}^2) \sum_{i=1,2} \sum_{|\alpha|=1}^3 \|D^\alpha \varphi_i\|_C^2 + \sum_{i=1,2} \|g_i\|_{C^1}^2 \right).$$

The main result is the following theorem.

Theorem 1. *Let the above Conditions 1 and 2 be satisfied for the coefficients of equation (1), and let the following inequalities be satisfied for the coefficients of the equation and their traces:*

$$2q < 1.$$

Then there exists a unique solution to problem (1)-(6) from the class U .

Remark 1. We can achieve the inequality $2q < 1$ by choosing the norms of f and g small, and taking g_i with its derivatives small, and also taking the derivatives of φ_i small.

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